

First Report of *Pleurotus cystidiosus* from Florida, USA

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Pleurotus cystidiosus is an edible species of mushroom that has been observed occurring outside of cultivation in Florida, U.S.A for the first time. Described from Indiana, this species is available through multiple online commercial retailers of inoculated spawn and spores. Relatives from the genus *Pleurotus* are known to readily escape cultivation and thrive in foreign environments, likely altering local ecosystems and possibly affecting fungal communities in habitats it is introduced into. The specimen mentioned was collected, sequenced, and morphologically described.

Keywords: *Pleurotus cystidiosus*, oyster mushroom, Florida, first report

Subject classification codes: include these here if the journal requires them

Introduction

Pleurotus cystidiosus, also known as the Abalone Oyster or Maple Oyster Mushroom, is a member of the Pleurotaceae first described from Indiana, U.S.A in 1969(1). The genus *Pleurotus* (Oyster Mushrooms) are widely known as choice edibles, with many species being commonly used as ‘home-grow kits’ where a colonized substrate in plastic is then fruited by the consumer and harvested for consumption (2). Oyster mushrooms’ rapid speed of colonization, ability to thrive on many substrates, and large fruiting bodies make them a great fit for this method of cultivation. Commonly cultivated *Pleurotus* species include *P. ostreatus* (Grey Oyster Mushroom), *P. citrinopileatus* (Golden Oyster Mushroom), *P. eringyi* (King Oyster Mushroom), and *P. djamor* (Pink Oyster Mushroom). *P. cystidiosus* is less commonly cultivated in the U.S than the above, but is still available and grown on a smaller scale.

The specimen in question was observed and collected by the first author on May 30th, 2022, on the campus of Florida Southern College in Lakeland, Florida. It was found just outside a campus greenhouse growing on an unidentified ornamental hardwood. This substrate is consistent with the saprotrophic ecology of *P. cystidiosus*.

Methods

Collection

Specimen was photographed and geotagged *in situ* on May 30th, 2022. It was then quickly dried after collection in a food dehydrator at approximately 50 C for around 24 hours and then stored in a plastic bag with silica gel packet. Images and description were uploaded to iNaturalist (observation #119550304) the next day.

Sequencing

The specimen was mailed to Ohio DNA Lab on September 25th, 2023, where DNA extraction, PCR, and Oxford Nanopore sequencing of the ITS1F and ITS4R region were carried out (3).

Microscopy

A small piece of the lamellae was cut from dried specimen, rehydrated in 10% KOH solution, and then stained with Congo Red and crush mounted. Section viewed using AccuScope 3012 microscope with 20x, 40x, and 100x objectives.

Analysis

Micrographs taken using AmScope software, spore dimensions made using PixiMetre.

Results

Morphology

Sessile white pileus covered with tan-brown scales, with solid brown portions at the margin and apex of the pileus. Margin slightly inrolled. Lamellae subdistant, white, and yellowing near the gill edge with age. Decurrent to attachment point on substrate.

Spores ellipsoid to subfusiform, hyaline in KOH. Basidia clavate, 4-sterigmate, with 2-4 spores.

Spores measure (11.5) 12.9 - 16.3 (17.4) \times (4.1) 4.6 - 6.4 (7.7) μm , Q = (1.9) 2.2 - 3.5 (3.6); N = 23, Me = 14.8 \times 5.4 μm ; Qe = 2.8 (Piximetre)

Sequencing

Results were communicated in March 2024 on iNaturalist, confirming the species ID as *Pleurotus cystidiosus* and the observation as the first known occurrence of the species in Florida. Sequence reported as having a 15BP insertion but otherwise consistent with known sequences in GenBank. Sequence linked at bottom of paper in 'Data' section.

Discussion

The genus *Pleurotus* is of significant commercial value as a choice edible and has been expanding across local markets in the U.S in recent years. It is considered the second most commonly cultivated group of mushrooms worldwide following *Agaricus bisporus* (2,4). This has led to higher demand and the popularity of 'at-home' grow kits for various *Pleurotus* species. Some of these, notably *P. citrinopileatus*, are known to readily escape cultivation and prosper in non-native environments (5). Should this be the case for *P. cystidiosus* in Florida, it would be worth tracking its spread and monitoring its impact on local ecosystems and fungal diversity. Other publications have established novel sightings of this species in Cuba and Pakistan (6,7). This publication represents the first confirmed sighting of this species in Florida. Being found in Central Florida with no prior sightings in the more northern regions of FL may indicate that *P. cystidiosus* has not gradually spread southward through natural dispersal but through human intervention. Further study may include a deeper analysis of the 15 base pair abnormality found in the ITS sequence of the studied material and/or a phylogenetic analysis of this material and allied taxa.

Works Cited

1. Miller Jr., O. K. A New Species of *Pleurotus* with a Coremioid Imperfect Stage. *Mycologia* 61, 887–893 (1969).
2. Sánchez, C. Cultivation of *Pleurotus ostreatus* and other edible mushrooms. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 85, 1321–1337 (2010).
3. Canan, K. et al. Introducing the Ohio Mushroom DNA Lab: Early Lessons and Contributions from a New Community-Driven Nanopore Sequencing Laboratory. (2024).
4. Zervakis, G. I., Moncalvo, J.-M. & Vilgalys, R. Molecular phylogeny, biogeography and speciation of the mushroom species *Pleurotus cystidiosus* and allied taxa. *Microbiology* 150, 715–726 (2004).
5. Bruce, A. L. Population genomic insights into the establishment of non-native golden oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus citrinopileatus*) in the United States. (2018).
6. Hussain, S., Afshan, N.-U.-S., Ahmad, H. & Khalid, A. N. New report of the edible mushroom *Pleurotus cystidiosus* from Pakistan. (2015).
7. Vilaró, M. C., Hernández, N. B. & Portales, J. M. First Cuban record of *Pleurotus cystidiosus* (Agaricales: Pleurotaceae) and its asexual morph - Primer registro de *Pleurotus cystidiosus* (Agaricales: Pleurotaceae) y su morfo asexual. *Revista del Jardín Botánico Nacional* 39, 75–77 (2018).

Data & Figures

Figure 1. *P. cystidiosus* in situ on an unknown tree planted on Florida Southern College campus in Lakeland, Florida. Top view of pileus (left) and lower view of hymenium (right).

Figure 2. Four-sterigmate basidia with three attached spores visible. Stained with Congo Red, viewed in 10% KOH solution. Brightfield, 1000x oil

Figure 3. Two views of basidia without spores present. Specimens prepared like Figure 2. Phase contrast, 40x.

Data

iNaturalist observation: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/119550304>

DNA Barcode ITS: https://mycomap.com/genetics/sequences/ont_sequences/e01-omdl04211-inat119550304-1-r118858/

Thank you to Kyle Canan of the Ohio Mushroom DNA Lab for extracting, amplifying, and sequencing the specimen free of charge. Thank you to the team of sequence validators who work with OMDL as well for aligning and validating the ITS sequence.